

A Better Approximation to Uniform Revolving Scanning

L Lindegren (1982 June 2)

Lund Observatory
Box 1107
S-22104 LUND, Sweden

A previous note, "Selection of Scanning Law Parameters (K, ξ)" (1982 May 19), contained an expression for the speed of the z axis on the sky, eqn (6) in that note, which is unfortunately incorrect. The exact expression is

$$v = \dot{\lambda}_s [\cos^2 v + \left(\frac{dv}{d\lambda_s} \sin \xi - \cos \xi \sin v\right)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

which with the proposed formula for $v(\lambda_s)$ gives however a higher $v_{\max}$ than according to eqn (8) or Table 1 in that note.

The variations in v can be completely eliminated by successively incrementing v according to the differential equation

$$\dot{v} = \operatorname{cosec} \xi [v^2 - (\dot{\lambda}_s \cos v)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \dot{\lambda}_s \cot \xi \sin v. \quad (2)$$

A disadvantage is then that no explicit (or simple, at least) expression exists for $v(t)$. Alternatively, if we can accept variations by $\pm 1.7\%$ due to the eccentricity of Earth's orbit, then an explicit expression can readily be obtained by putting $v/\dot{\lambda}_s = \text{const}$. Eqn (3) in the previous note is then replaced by

$$v = \bar{v} + a_1 \cos \bar{v} + a_2 \sin(2\bar{v}) + a_3 \cos(3\bar{v}) + a_4 \sin(4\bar{v}) + \dots \quad (3)$$

where the coefficients are obtained as functions of $c \equiv \cos \xi$ and $u \equiv K \sin \xi$:

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= -\frac{c}{u} + \frac{5c+4c^3}{16u^3} - 0.24 u^{-5} & (= -0.16378 \text{ for } K = 6.4, \xi = 43^\circ) \\ a_2 &= -\frac{1+2c^2}{8u^2} + \frac{7c^2+3c^4}{24u^4} - 0.18 u^{-6} & (= -0.01308 \quad - " -) \\ a_3 &= \frac{5c+4c^3}{48u^3} - 0.12 u^{-5} & (= 0.00123 \quad - " -) \\ a_4 &= \frac{7c^2+3c^4}{96u^4} - 0.06 u^{-6} & (= 0.00012 \quad - " -) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

etc. The resulting constant value of $v/\dot{\lambda}_s$ is

$$v/\dot{\lambda}_s = u + \frac{1+2c^2}{4u} + \frac{1-20c^2-8c^4}{64u^3} + 0.13 u^{-5} \quad (= 4.48117 \text{ for } K = 6.4, \xi = 43^\circ) \quad (5)$$

A revised Table 1 is given below. Table 2 shows the residual variation of $v/\dot{\lambda}_s$ for the case $(K, \xi) = (6.4, 43^\circ)$ when truncating (3) after $a_n \cos(n\bar{v})$.

Table 1. Minimum revolving angle ($\xi_{\min}$) versus K, value according to the rule $\xi = 275^\circ/K$, and the corresponding range of z axis speed ($v_{\min}$, $v_{\max}$) for revolving angle $275^\circ/K$.

K	$\xi_{\min}$	$\xi = 275^\circ/ K ^{-1}$	$\dot{v}_{\min}$	$v_{\max}$
5.8	44.84 ^o	47.41 ^o	4.245 ^o /day	4.390 ^o /day
5.9	44.06	46.61	4.263	4.408
6.0	43.31	45.83	4.280	4.425
6.1	42.59	45.08	4.296	4.442
6.2	41.89	44.35	4.311	4.458
6.3	41.21	43.65	4.326	4.474
6.33333	40.99	43.42	4.331	4.478
6.4	40.55	42.97	4.341	4.488
6.5	39.92	42.31	4.354	4.502
6.6	39.30	41.67	4.367	4.516
6.7	38.71	41.04	4.379	4.528
6.8	38.13	40.44	4.391	4.540

Table 2. Variation of $f \equiv v/\lambda_s$ when terms up to and including $a_n \cos(n\bar{v})$ are used in the Fourier series for v , eqn (3). Hølg's approximation is $a_1 = -c/u$, $a_2, a_3, \dots = 0$. ($K = 6.4$, $\xi = 43^\circ$)

n	$f_{\min}$	$f_{\max}$	amplitude	$\langle f \rangle$
0	3.6334	5.0961	±16.3 %	4.4625
1	4.3483	4.5922	± 2.7 %	4.4794
2	4.4625	4.4982	± 0.40 %	4.4811
3	4.4786	4.4836	± 0.06 %	4.4812
4	4.4808	4.4816	± 0.01 %	4.4812
Hølg's approx.	4.3648	4.5962	± 2.6 %	4.4807